

Variation in PACU pain onset in surgical patients who received a peripheral nerve block: Differences in block location and local anesthetic used

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Background

Nerve blocks are a vital component of perioperative pain management. Some nerve blocks are more difficult to perform than others due to their anatomical location. This abstract aims to delineate the differences between nerve block location and local anesthetic (LA) used in understanding the variation of pain onset in the postanesthesia care unit (PACU).

Methods

Over a period of 4 months, patients who received a peripheral nerve block for perioperative pain were called within 48hrs of their surgery via telephone and asked standardized questions regarding their pain status in the PACU. The data was then sorted according to what type of block was performed (Upper extremity[UE]{Supraclavicular, Interscalene, Intercostobrachial,}, Lower extremity[LE]{Femoral, Sciatic, Adductor Canal, Popliteal, Fascia Iliaca}, and Other{TAPs, PECs I & II, ESP, QL}) and the type of LA that was used (0.5% Bupivacaine, 0.25% Bupivacaine, and Mepivacaine/Bupivacaine).

Findings

The total percentage of patients that experience postoperative pain in the PACU was 35.54% with an average subjective pain score of 6.5/10 (n=127). Of the UE nerve blocks, Supraclavicular & Intercostobrachial and Interscalene+, 6.7% and 16.67% of patients experienced pain in the PACU respectively (n=21). The subjective pain scores of the respective UE blocks were 8/10 and 9/10 respectively. Of the LE nerve blocks, Femoral+, Popliteal+, and Fascia Iliaca, 42.86%, 0%, and 33.33% of patients experienced pain in the PACU respectively (n=19). The subjective pain scores of the respective LE blocks were 6.3/10, n/a, and 6/10. Other nerve blocks include TAPs, PECs I & II, ESP, and QL. Of these respective nerve blocks, 36.59%, 60.87%, 50%, and 40% of patients experienced pain in the PACU (n=72). The respective subjective pain scores were 6.4/10, 6.7/10, 6.5/10, and 5/10 respectively.

When it comes to the LA used; 0.5% Bupivacaine, 0.25% Bupivacaine, and Mepivacaine/Bupivacaine, 32.14%, 47.54%, and 0% of patients experienced postoperative pain in the PACU respectively (n=97). The respective subjective pain scores were 5.8/10, 6.8/10 and n/a.

Conclusion

There is large variation in patients that experience postoperative pain in the PACU versus those who do not which seems to be correlated with the local anesthetic used and the location of the nerve block. When it comes to the LA used, there appears to be a dose-dependent correlation between medication concentration and perceived postoperative pain. A smaller percentage of patients experienced postoperative pain in the 0.5% vs 0.25% Bupivacaine group and with a lower subjective pain intensity. There does not appear to be an apparent correlation between UE vs LE vs Other nerve blocks when it comes to pain in the PACU.

PACU Pain Status (n=127)

